

1 **Production of hydrochar fuel by microwave-hydrothermal carbonisation of olive**
2 **pomace slurry from olive oil industry for combustion application**

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13 **Abstract**

14 This work is a pioneering investigation on microwave-assisted hydrothermal
15 carbonization (MHTC) of real olive pomace (OP) slurry from olive oil industry to produce
16 hydrochars with improved fuel characteristics for combustion applications (e.g. in
17 boilers). Experiments were conducted based on the central composite design of response
18 surface methodology, with two main process variables: temperature (180–250 °C) and
19 holding time (2–30 min). Severity factors ($\log R_0$) were calculated from the
20 aforementioned variables and used to explain the process impact in a simpler way. The
21 elevation of MHTC severity led to significant modifications in the structure of OP
22 (studied through FTIR and NMR analyses), as well as reductions in yield, bulk density,
23 volatile matter, and ash content in the hydrochars. High-severity hydrochar was

24 positioned in the lignite zone (van Krevelen diagram). It also exhibited substantial
25 reductions in the alkali index (86.53%), slagging index (76.89%), and fouling index
26 (96.07%), compared to the raw material. Overall, the best conditions for hydrochar
27 production with improved combustion characteristics were found to be 250 °C for 30 min
28 (HHV = 28.45 MJ/kg, energy densification ratio = 1.25, equilibrium moisture content =
29 31.1 mg/g, comprehensive combustibility index = $2.94 \cdot 10^{-7} \%^2 \text{ min}^{-2} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-3}$). These
30 attributes demonstrate that high-severity hydrochars could be utilized as biofuel for
31 energy applications.

32 **Keywords:** Olive pomace; Microwave hydrothermal carbonisation; Hydrochar; Biofuel;
33 Bioenergy.

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46 **Nomenclature**

OP = Olive pomace	250-30 = Hydrochar produced at 250 °C with 30 min holding time
HTC = Hydrothermal carbonisation	Log R ₀ = Severity factor
MHTC = Microwave assisted hydrothermal carbonisation	AIL = Acid insoluble lignin
180-2 = Hydrochar produced at 180 °C with 2 min holding time	HY = Hydrochar yield
180-16 = Hydrochar produced at 180 °C with 16 min holding time	VM = Volatile matter
180-30 = Hydrochar produced at 180 °C with 30 min holding time	FC = Fixed carbon
215-2 = Hydrochar produced at 215 °C with 2 min holding time	EMC = Equilibrium moisture content
215-16 = Hydrochar produced at 215 °C with 16 min holding time	HHV = Higher heating value
215-30 = Hydrochar produced at 215 °C with 30 min holding time	LHV = Lower heating value
250-2 = Hydrochar produced at 250 °C with 2 min holding time	EDR = Energy densification ratio
250-16 = Hydrochar produced at 250 °C with 16 min holding time	EY = Energy yield
	AI = Alkali index
	B/A = Base to acid ratio
	SI = Slagging index
	FI = Fouling index
	SVI = Slag viscosity index
	BAI = Bed agglomeration index

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50 **1. Introduction**

51 Fossil fuels are non-renewable and the main source (75%) of greenhouse gas emissions
52 [1]. Therefore, use of clean renewable energy is crucial to saving the environment and
53 life on earth [2]. The European Union (EU) renewable energy directive II (2018/2001/EU)
54 mandates biofuel production from non-edible lignocellulosic biomass, preferably
55 abundant and domestically available biomass [3]. Pyrolysis is the commonly used process
56 for biofuel production, which involves thermally heating dry biomass in the absence of
57 oxygen. It converts biomass into energy-dense biochar for biofuel applications [4].
58 However, for treating wet biomass with high water content (e.g., sewage sludge, food
59 waste), hydrothermal carbonization (HTC), also known as wet pyrolysis, is a preferred
60 method. In this method, energy consuming steps like dewatering and oven drying of
61 biomass are not required. Wet biomass is directly pyrolyzed (150–250 °C) to produce
62 hydrochar with a high calorific value for solid biofuel applications [5]. In prior art, HTC
63 using conventional heating systems was mainly reported [6]. The conventional system
64 involves surface heat transfer mechanisms, i.e., conduction and convection, but has
65 limitations such as longer heat exchange times and non-uniform heating. To overcome
66 these limitations, several studies have recently explored microwave-assisted
67 hydrothermal carbonization (MHTC) of biomass [7,8]. A microwave system works on a
68 dielectric heating mechanism, which involves microwave radiation heating the biomass
69 particles. It provides the benefits of more uniform heating, faster heat exchange time,
70 shorter processing time, and more controlled heating [9]. However, studies on the MHTC
71 of biomasses are limited [10] and could be extended to investigate unexplored biomass
72 like olive pomace (OP).

73 The olive oil industry produces a large quantity of OP (olive pulp and seeds) slurry as a
74 residue after the extraction of olive oil. This material contains a very high amount of water

75 and environmentally toxic organic contaminants like phenols [11]. Thus, the disposal and
76 management of OP slurry are very challenging. The EU is the leading producer (68%) of
77 olive oil globally, with a production of approx. 2 million tonnes per year [12].
78 Consequently, OP biomass is indigenously available in abundance. In addition, its
79 lignocellulosic composition shows its potential to be a suitable feedstock for the
80 production of hydrochar for biofuel applications. Research on real OP slurry from the
81 olive oil industry for hydrochar production is highly scarce, and mainly reported the use
82 of conventional heating systems at different process conditions such as 180–300 °C
83 temperature and 0–24 h holding times [13–19]. They reported the production of
84 hydrochar with a higher heating value of approx. 25–32 MJ/kg that is comparable to coal.
85 Regarding the use of microwave technology, Kostas et al. (2020) only documented the
86 microwave dry pyrolysis (150–900 W for 20–240 sec) of OP to produce biochar for its
87 application as an adsorbent [20]. In the literature, the MHTC of wet OP has not yet been
88 reported. Furthermore, the impact of HTC conditions on OP hydrochar properties was
89 also not explained using severity factors. Equilibrium moisture content data was also not
90 provided, which is a very important property that affects not only the energy value of the
91 fuels but also their storage, transportation, and handling [21]. Data on the corrosive
92 elements (mainly Na and K) present in the OP hydrochar and the assessment of slagging
93 and fouling risks caused by them were not reported. The slagging-fouling risk assessment
94 of hydrochar fuel is crucial to predicting its negative impact (reactor material
95 deterioration) on the combustion boilers and deciding a suitable strategy for its practically
96 feasible application. Optimization of the HTC process is also rarely reported and has not
97 been done using the widely recommended response surface methodology [22].

98 To resolve the aforementioned research gaps, the present study aims to evaluate the
99 MHTC process for transforming industrial OP slurry into hydrochars with improved fuel

100 characteristics for combustion applications, preferably in boilers. The main objectives of
101 this work are: 1) to determine the effect of MHTC conditions on the hydrochar
102 characteristics with the use of severity factors; 2) to establish the slagging and fouling
103 risks for the OP and its hydrochars; 3) to predict the optimal conditions for the MHTC
104 process on the basis of response surface methodology to produce hydrochar with the best
105 combustion characteristics; and 4) to compare the combustion performance of the OP and
106 its best hydrochar using TG-DSC analysis.

107 **2. Materials and Methods**

108 **2.1 Raw material**

109 The wet OP (fruit variety '*Picual*') samples, in slurry form with a water content of
110 $80.43 \pm 0.17\%$, were collected through a random sampling method from Almazara Andrés
111 Aguilar, a local olive oil mill situated in the Linares (Jaen), Spain (UTM coordinates:
112 $38^{\circ}04'26.86''$ N, $3^{\circ}38'52.31''$ W).

113 **2.2 Experiments for MHTC of wet OP**

114 The experimental design for MHTC of wet OP slurry was based on the response surface
115 methodology (RSM), using a face-centered central composite design (CCD) with three
116 central points. The two experimental variables (temperature and holding time) were
117 varied at three levels, and for each operational condition, three replicates were carried
118 out, resulting in a total of thirty-three MHTC experiments. Table S1 (Supplementary
119 Information) shows the resulting matrix for the experimental design, including both the
120 coded and real values of the two independent variables. The MHTC was done in a high-
121 performance microwave digestion system (Milestone Ethos One) with an ATC-400
122 temperature sensor and APC-55E automatic pressure control. Based on CCD,
123 experiments were conducted with wet OP under varied temperatures of 180–250 °C and

124 holding times of 2–30 minutes. The selection of the temperature range for MHTC in the
125 present study was based on earlier studies [13,18]. Other fixed process parameters were
126 1500 W microwave energy, a heating rate of 22 °C/minute, and a 50% stirring capacity.
127 After MHTC, the hydrochars were separated from the liquid phase by the vacuum
128 filtration method at room temperature. Thereafter, hydrochars were air-dried to reduce
129 the moisture content and then stored in sealed plastic bags. Abbreviations used for
130 hydrochar samples in the present article were based on MHTC temperature (°C) and
131 holding time (min): 180-2, 180-16, 180-30, 215-2, 215-16, 215-30, 250-2, 250-16, and
132 250-30. For example, 180-2 means hydrochar produced at 180 °C with a 2 min holding
133 time.

134 The CCD preparation for MHTC experiments and data analysis were done using Modde
135 6.0 statistical software (Umetric AB, Umeå, Sweden). A second-order polynomial model
136 (Eq. 1) was followed to study the effect of independent variables on four responses:
137 hydrochar yield (HY), equilibrium moisture content (EMC), and higher and lower heating
138 values of hydrochars (HHV and LHV, respectively).

$$Y = \beta_0 + (\beta_1 \cdot T_R) + (\beta_2 \cdot t_R) + (\beta_3 \cdot T_R \cdot T_R) + (\beta_4 \cdot t_R \cdot t_R) + (\beta_5 \cdot T_R \cdot t_R) \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

139 where Y is the response value, T_R and t_R are the real values of the two independent
140 variables, and β_i ($i = 1-5$) are the intercept term (β_0), the linear effects (β_1 and β_2), the
141 squared effects (β_3 and β_4) and the interaction effects (β_5) calculated from the
142 experimental data by regression analysis. The statistical validation was performed by a
143 one-way ANOVA test with a 95% confidence level.

144 **2.3. Severity factor calculation**

145 The severity factor ($\log R_0$) is a very useful parameter to study the combined effect of
146 temperature and reaction time in the hydrothermal treatment of lignocellulosic biomass.

147 The calculation of $\log R_0$ is based on Eq. 2 [23]. Where t represents the process time
148 (min), $T(t)$ is the temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at a specific time, T_r is the reference temperature (100
149 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), w is the activation energy (equal to 14.75 for biomass), and e is the natural base.
150 Because the experiments were not conducted at a constant temperature during both the
151 initial (heating) and final (cooling) stages, the severity factor for each operating condition
152 was calculated as the sum of the severity factors determined during the heating,
153 maintenance, and cooling stages (Eq. 3).

$$154 \quad R_0 = \int_0^t e^{\frac{T(t)-T_r}{w}} dt \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

$$155 \quad R_0 = (R_0)_{\text{heating}} + (R_0)_{\text{maintenance}} + (R_0)_{\text{cooling}} \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

156 **2.4 Characterisation of raw material and hydrochar**

157 Hydrochar yield (%) was calculated from the dry weight of hydrochar and raw OP
158 biomass [24]. Extractive content in the samples was determined using the hexane
159 extraction method [25]. The cellulose and hemicellulose were estimated by the detergent
160 method [26], and the acid-insoluble lignin (AIL) was determined by the TAPPI t 222 os-
161 74 method [27]. The bulk density (BD) is measured by the ratio of the dry weight of
162 samples to the volume they occupy [28]. Proximate analysis was done by a gravimetric
163 method to estimate moisture, volatile matter (VM), fixed carbon (FC), and ash contents.
164 Moisture (M) content in the samples was determined by oven drying at 105 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ until a
165 constant weight was achieved. The VM was determined by heating samples in a ceramic
166 crucible with a lid at 900 ± 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a furnace [29]. The ash content was estimated by
167 heating samples at 575 ± 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5 h in an open crucible in the muffle furnace according
168 to the NREL/TP-510-42622 method [30]. The FC content in the samples was calculated
169 using Eq. 4. Ultimate analysis of samples was performed using an CHNS elemental

170 automatic elemental analyzer (TruSpec Micro, Leco, USA) to determine total carbon (C),
 171 hydrogen (H), nitrogen (N), and sulphur (S) content. Oxygen (O) content was indirectly
 172 calculated through the subtraction method (Eq. 5). The Bomb Calorimeter (Parr Series
 173 6400, USA) was used to quantify the calorific value (HHV) of the raw material and
 174 hydrochar samples. The lower heating value (LHV) of samples was estimated using Eq.
 175 6 [31]. Surface functional groups in raw material and hydrochars were identified using
 176 fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (Vertex 70 spectrophotometer, Bruker, USA)
 177 analysis in the 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} wavelength range with 4 cm^{-1} resolution and 100 scans.
 178 Solid state ^{13}C NMR analysis of samples was performed using an NMR
 179 spectrophotometer (Bruker AVANCE, USA) with a CP-MAS probe (4 mm) operating at
 180 100.62 MHz, 2 ms contact time, and 1200 scans. The energy densification ratio (EDR)
 181 and energy yield (EY) of raw material and hydrochar samples were calculated using Eqs.
 182 7 and 8 [18].

$$183 \quad \text{FC (\%)} = 100 - (\text{M\%} + \text{VM\%} + \text{Ash\%}) \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

$$184 \quad \text{O(\%)} = 100 - (\text{C\%} + \text{H\%} + \text{N\%} + \text{S\%} + \text{Ash\%}) \quad \text{Eq. (5)}$$

$$185 \quad \text{LHV (Btu/lb)} = \text{HHV (Btu/lb)} - 10.55(\text{M\%} + 9\text{H\%}) \quad \text{Eq. (6)}$$

$$186 \quad \text{EDR} = \frac{\text{HHV}_{\text{dried hydrochar}}}{\text{HHV}_{\text{dried olive pomace}}} \quad \text{Eq. (7)}$$

$$187 \quad \text{EY (\%)} = \text{Hydrochar yield} \times \text{EDR} \quad \text{Eq. (8)}$$

188 **2.5 Equilibrium moisture content determination**

189 The equilibrium moisture content (EMC) is an essential parameter used to evaluate the
 190 water sorption behavior of a porous material [21]. It was determined by measuring the
 191 changes in moisture uptake by the dry olive pomace biomass and hydrochars after
 192 exposing them to equilibrium conditions for several days. Experiments were conducted

193 at 30 °C and 75% relative humidity. The relative humidity of 75% was achieved by using
 194 NaCl salt solutions [28]. The tests were carried out in triplicate, and the weights of the
 195 biomass and hydrochars were measured daily until no significant changes were observed.
 196 Results are reported on a moisture-free dry basis (mg of water adsorbed per gram of dry
 197 biomass).

198 **2.6 Slagging and fouling risks evaluation**

199 The OP and hydrochars samples were digested using HNO₃+H₂O₂ mixture (3:1 ratio) in
 200 a microwave digestion system (ETHOS One, Milestone) at 140 °C, followed by ICP-OES
 201 analysis, and using conversion factors to quantify metal oxides (Table S2, Supplementary
 202 Information). The slagging and fouling risks were evaluated based on their mineral
 203 composition and use of empirical indices (Table 1) such as alkali index (AI), base-to-acid
 204 ratio, (B/A), slagging index (SI), fouling index (FI), slag viscosity index (SVI), and bed
 205 agglomeration index (BAI) [32–34].

206 Table 1. Methods for calculation of slagging and fouling indices

Indicator	Equations	Slagging and Fouling risks		
		Low	Medium	High
Alkali index (AI)	$AI \text{ (kg/G)} = \frac{Na_2O + K_2O}{HHV \text{ (GJ/kg)}}$	<0.17	0.17-0.34	>0.34
Base to acid ratio (B/A)	$B/A = \frac{Fe_2O_3 + CaO + MgO + Na_2O + K_2O + P_2O_5}{SiO_2 + Al_2O_3 + TiO_2}$	-	-	-
Slagging index (SI)	$SI = B/A \times S\%$	<0.6	0.6-2.0	2.0-2.6
Fouling index (FI)	$FI = B/A \times (Na_2O\% + K_2O\%)$	0.2	0.2-0.5	0.5-1.0

Slag	viscosity	$SVI = SiO_2 \times 100$	>72	65-72	<65
	index (SVI)				
Bed		$BAI = \frac{Fe_2O_3}{Na_2O + K_2O}$	-	-	<0.15
	agglomeration				
	index (BAI) [33]				

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208 2.7 Combustion performance assessment using TG-DSC

209 The combustion behavior of samples was evaluated in an oxidative atmosphere by a
 210 thermogravimetric (TG) analyzer (TDA/SDTA 851e, Mettler Toledo, USA). The analysis
 211 conditions were 150 mL/min air flow and a 25–900 °C temperature range with a 10
 212 °C/min heating rate. Analysis was also performed by a differential scanning calorimeter
 213 (DSC 822e, Mettler Toledo, USA) under oxidative conditions. The ignition temperature
 214 (T_i) was determined from the DTG curve, where weight loss is 1%/min after the first
 215 weight loss due to the presence of residual moisture, while the shutdown temperature (T_f)
 216 is the temperature at which the DTG reaches 1%/min at the end of the curve [35]. The
 217 thermal reactivity of the samples was assessed using the comprehensive combustibility
 218 index (S), which was determined using Eq. 9 [36]. This equation includes the maximum
 219 (dw/dt) and average rates (dw/dt) of weight loss (wt%/min).

$$220 \quad S = \frac{(dw/dt)_{\max} (dw/dt)_{\text{mean}}}{T_i^2 T_f} \quad \text{Eq. (9)}$$

221 3. Results and Discussions

222 3.1 Structural composition of raw material and hydrochars

223 The holocellulose (sum of cellulose and hemicellulose), AIL, and extractive contents in
 224 the dry OP and hydrochar samples produced at different severity factors are shown in
 225 Table S2. In the present study, the severity factors are as follows: 3.050 (180°C-2 min),

226 3.633 (180°C-16 min), 3.874 (180°C-30 min), 4.015 (215°C-2 min), 4.647 (215°C-16
227 min), 4.895 (215°C-30 min), 5.071 (250°C-2 min), 5.684 (250°C-16 min), and 5.929
228 (250°C-30 min). The increase in temperature and holding time combined resulted in an
229 increment in severity factor values [37]. The dry OP consisted of higher holocellulose
230 (37.53%), followed by AIL (36.82%), and extractive contents (11.50%). The
231 holocellulose was comprised of more hemicellulose (25.39%) fractions than cellulose
232 (12.15%). In comparison to these results, Cequier et al. (2019) earlier reported a similar
233 amount of AIL (37±3.9%), lesser holocellulose (17.6±2.0%), and higher extractive
234 content (20±1.1%) in the OP [38]. The variations could be mainly due to differences in
235 the proportion of pulp, stone, and extractives in the dry OP.

236 The MHTC produced OP hydrochars with a reduced holocellulose content (2.06–
237 30.85%). In this holocellulose, the amount of hemicellulose in the hydrochars obtained at
238 3.874, 4.895, and 5.929 severity factors were relatively lower, i.e., 14.14%, 1.70%, and
239 0.0%, respectively. This indicated that hemicellulose could easily hydrolyze at a higher
240 HTC temperature and a longer holding time, which could be a main reason for reduction
241 of holocellulose content in hydrochars. However, AIL (46.17–64.30%) and extractive
242 (17.62–23.97%) fractions were enriched. Compared to dry OP, an increase in severity
243 factor (3.05 to 5.93) resulted in a 26.33–74.60% increase in AIL and a 53.18–108.37%
244 increase in extractive content. The hydrochar produced at a severity factor of 5.929
245 contained relatively higher AIL (64.30%) and extractives (23.75%), at the expense of
246 lower holocellulose (2.96%) contents. This is a favorable attribute of hydrochar for
247 biofuel application because higher lignin and extractives could increase its heating value
248 [39,40]. In agreement with present results, Najafi et al. (2021) also reported the same
249 impact of the increasing severity factor on holocellulose, lignin, and extractive fractions
250 in OP hydrochars [41].

251 The FTIR and solid C-13 NMR spectra were used to determine the impact of MHTC on
252 the surface functional groups of dry OP. In Fig. S1, the FTIR spectra of OP biomass and
253 hydrochars are shown in the range of 400–4000 cm^{-1} . Whereas in Fig. 1, the same spectra
254 were presented in the range of 900–1800 cm^{-1} for a better interpretation of the spectral
255 signals. This specific region showed the most significant changes in intensities and
256 positions of spectral signals, which are characteristic of the structural components of
257 biomass (hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin). In the case of hemicellulose, the peak at
258 1236 cm^{-1} has been associated with C–O–C bonds of acetyl groups [42], while the peak
259 at 1740 cm^{-1} could be attributed to the vibrational stretching of the C=O present in acetoxy
260 groups of xylans [43]. The increase in temperature and holding time resulted in a decrease
261 in the intensity of peak at 1236 cm^{-1} , especially in the hydrochars produced at 215 °C and
262 250 °C. Whereas, the peak intensity at 1742 cm^{-1} significantly reduced in hydrochars 250-
263 16 and 250-30. This indicated a substantial loss of hemicellulose in the hydrochars. With
264 respect to cellulose, the intense peak centered at 1030 cm^{-1} has been associated with its
265 C-O bonds [43]. The increase in MHTC severity generally led to the attenuation of this
266 peak signal, and resulting in the appearance of a new peak (1056 cm^{-1}) in the spectra of
267 hydrochars. This new peak corresponds to C-H bonds and could be formed due to
268 hydrothermal treatment of cellulose fractions [37]. On the other hand, FTIR spectra in the
269 lignin fingerprint region (1000–1800 cm^{-1}) revealed that the increase in MHTC severity
270 led to the production of hydrochars enriched in lignin. The peak at 1708 cm^{-1} could be
271 attributed to stretching vibrations in unconjugated carbonyl bonds of aldehydes or
272 ketones, while the peaks at 1605 cm^{-1} and 1514 cm^{-1} are usually assigned to C=C bonds
273 in aromatic rings [44]. The peaks at 1455 cm^{-1} and 1110 cm^{-1} are of C-H bonds in methyl
274 groups of lignin [44]. All these peaks signals were enhanced with the increase in the
275 severity of the MHTC indicating a progressive enrichment of lignin in hydrochars.

276 Furthermore, a decrease in peak intensity at 1645 cm^{-1} that is characteristic of H-O-H
277 bonds in adsorbed water [45] was observed. This suggested that the EMC in the
278 hydrochars decreased with the increasing severity of the MHTC, and supported the earlier
279 findings on EMC (discussed in Section 3.3).

280

281 **Figure 1.** FTIR spectra of raw material and hydrochars.

282 The solid-state ^{13}C -NMR spectra (Figure 2) of OP and hydrochars showed the presence
283 of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. The peaks at 57–67 ppm (corresponding to O-
284 alkyl carbons, C6), 70 ppm (C2,3,5), 80–92 ppm (OCH groups, C4), 102–108 ppm (C1)
285 and 170 ppm (C=O groups) were signals of cellulose and hemicellulose. The C4 signals
286 at 80–85 and 85–92 ppm were indicative of amorphous and crystalline cellulose,
287 respectively [46]. Characteristic signals at 20 ppm (methyl), and 30 ppm (aliphatic

288 methylene carbons) were of hemicellulose [47,48]. Signals at 52–56 ppm (OCH₃), 100–
289 112 ppm (acetal, C1), 135 ppm (aromatic C), and 142–160 ppm (aromatic C) were
290 attributed to lignin [46,49]. The MHTC of OP resulted in changes in the hydrochars
291 spectra. Compared to OP spectra, the peak intensities at 20 ppm and 173 ppm decreased,
292 and the peak intensity at 30 ppm increased and sharpened in the hydrochars produced at
293 180 °C-30 min onwards. This could indicate that the depolymerization of hemicellulose
294 intensified at 180 °C-30 min. Furthermore, an increase in MHTC severity resulted in a
295 decrease in the peak intensity of amorphous cellulose (80–85 ppm), while the crystalline
296 cellulose peak intensity (85–92 ppm) sharpened and increased relatively. In addition, an
297 increase in the peak's intensity at 55 ppm (prominently 215 °C-30 min onwards), 135
298 ppm, and 152 ppm indicated the gradual enrichment of lignin fractions with an elevation
299 of MHTC severity. The lignin enrichment was more prominently observed in hydrochars
300 produced at 250 °C. The reduction in hemicellulose fraction could be due to its conversion
301 into degradation products such as monosaccharides, oligosaccharides, and furfurals [50].
302 In the literature, authors have also earlier reported a decrease in hemicellulose and
303 amorphous cellulose signals, and enrichment of lignin in the solid-state ¹³C-NMR
304 analysis of hydrochars produced from olive tree trimmings [51] and textile waste [52], or
305 maple wood chars [53].

306

307 **Figure 2.** NMR spectra of raw material and hydrochars. The C, H, and L represents
 308 cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin, respectively.

309 **3.2 Physical, proximate, and ultimate characteristics of raw material and**
 310 **hydrochars.**

311 **Table 2.** Physical and proximate characteristics of raw material and hydrochars on a dry
 312 basis.

Samples	HY (%)	BD (g cm ⁻³)	Ash (%)	VM (%)	FC (%)	FC/VM	References
OP	NA	0.52 ± 0.02	4.25 ± 0.14	80.31 ± 1.41	15.44 ± 1.54	0.19	Present work
OP	NA	NA	2.3	74.2	16.1	0.21	[13]
OP	NA	NA	9.0	66.7	16.6	0.24	[18]
OP	NA	NA	0.1	73.1	24.7	0.33	[54]
180-2	91.02 ± 1.77	0.37 ± 0.00	1.76 ± 0.37	79.06 ± 0.80	19.18 ± 1.11	0.24	Present work
180-16	91.24 ± 2.23	0.40 ± 0.01	1.99 ± 0.31	78.71 ± 0.47	19.30 ± 0.74	0.25	Present work
180-30	86.74 ± 0.79	0.38 ± 0.02	2.18 ± 0.22	77.94 ± 0.36	19.88 ± 0.30	0.26	Present work
215-2	71.06 ± 1.19	0.38 ± 0.04	2.28 ± 0.05	75.35 ± 0.68	22.37 ± 0.63	0.30	Present work
215-16	68.40 ± 1.98	0.30 ± 0.03	2.01 ± 0.28	75.09 ± 0.68	22.90 ± 0.68	0.30	Present work

215-16	67.57 ± 2.07	0.33 ± 0.04	2.42 ± 0.43	74.71 ± 0.47	22.87 ± 0.72	0.31	Present work
215-16	67.42 ± 2.97	0.32 ± 0.02	2.04 ± 0.05	74.93 ± 0.80	23.03 ± 0.82	0.31	Present work
215-30	54.71 ± 0.90	0.25 ± 0.00	1.93 ± 0.14	74.10 ± 1.30	23.98 ± 1.89	0.32	Present work
250-2	68.52 ± 1.59	0.25 ± 0.00	2.00 ± 0.09	71.05 ± 0.60	26.95 ± 0.56	0.38	Present work
250-16	63.32 ± 1.22	0.29 ± 0.03	2.03 ± 0.22	68.39 ± 0.65	29.58 ± 0.43	0.43	Present work
250-30	51.98 ± 1.11	0.28 ± 0.00	1.72 ± 0.17	68.17 ± 0.81	30.11 ± 0.67	0.44	Present work
250-30	56.0	NA	0.8	61.0	36.2	0.59	[13]
250-30	65.0	NA	5.4	56.9	36.1	0.63	[18]
220-90	65.8	NA	27.7	65.3	5.5	0.08	[54]
260-60	40.63±2.02	NA	NA	66.77 ± 0.42	NA	NA	[17]

313 **Note:** NA means Not available

314 Table 2 presents the variations in the physical and proximate characteristics of raw
315 material and hydrochars. The MHTC of wet OP produced hydrochars with 51.98–91.24%
316 yields, 0.25–0.40 g cm⁻³ BD, 68.17–79.06% VM, 1.72–2.42% ash, and 19.18–30.11% FC
317 contents. The elevation of the MHTC severity factor from 3.050 to 5.929 caused a
318 reduction in hydrochar yield of 0.24 to 42.89%. Likewise, compared to dry OP, the BD,
319 VM, and ash contents in hydrochars fall by 23.65–52.9%, 1.57–15.13%, and 42.97–
320 59.51%, respectively. On the contrary, the amount of FC in the hydrochars increased by
321 24.26–95.07%. These trends are due to the various reactions that occurred during the
322 MHTC of OP. Intensification of hydrolysis, depolymerization, dehydration,
323 decarboxylation, and deoxygenation reactions could be responsible for the decrease in
324 yield and VM. Whereas, escalation of polymerization and aromatization reactions could
325 be reasons for the increase in FC [52,55,56].

326 The fuel ratio (FC/VM) is a commonly used indicator that predicts the combustibility
327 potential of hydrochars [18]. The hydrochars showed a fuel ratio range of 0.24 to 0.44,
328 which was 26.24–129.84% higher than OP with a 0.19 fuel ratio. High severity factor of
329 MHTC led to the production of hydrochar with a lower VM and a higher FC.
330 Consequently, this hydrochar type showed a higher fuel ratio of 0.44 and better

331 combustibility potential. The present findings are in confirmation of earlier studies on
 332 hydrochars produced from OP and other residual biomasses [18,57]. Lower ash content
 333 in hydrochars could be due to thermal degradation, increased solubility, and the transfer
 334 of inorganic minerals from OP to the liquid fraction, with increased MHTC severity
 335 [58,59]. This is an important advantage of hydrochars compared to lignite coals, which
 336 have a high ash content of up to 29.08% [60]. Apart from the aforesaid positive
 337 characteristics of hydrochar, a non-favorable characteristic of lower BD was observed. A
 338 reduction in BD could be due to a decrease in VM and inorganic components [57]. It
 339 makes hydrochar more voluminous and bulkier. Therefore, pelletisation of hydrochars is
 340 highly recommended to reduce the cost of transportation and storage.

341 **Table 3.** Ultimate characteristics of raw material and hydrochars on a dry basis.

Samples	C (%)	H (%)	N (%)	O (%)	References
OP	57.44 ± 0.98	7.39 ± 0.14	1.48 ± 0.35	29.31 ± 1.29	Present work
OP	48.30	6.73	1.26	43.71	[16]
OP	46.6	5.9	1.4	NA	[54]
OP	53.86±0.12	7.28±0.02	1.13±0.03	37.53±0.11	[17]
OP	42.80	5.65	2.01	46.51	[15]
180-2	58.03 ± 0.55	7.53 ± 0.01	1.84 ± 0.13	30.63 ± 0.52	Present work
180-16	59.87 ± 1.23	7.78 ± 0.22	1.73 ± 0.17	28.75 ± 1.93	Present work
180-30	61.60 ± 0.01	7.92 ± 0.10	1.89 ± 0.03	26.42 ± 0.24	Present work
215-2	62.42 ± 2.75	7.90 ± 0.49	1.62 ± 0.03	25.77 ± 3.13	Present work
215-16	61.94 ± 1.25	7.57 ± 0.28	1.60 ± 0.12	27.02 ± 1.45	Present work
215-16	63.66 ± 1.25	7.73 ± 0.22	1.63 ± 0.09	24.30 ± 1.52	Present work

215-16	63.30 ± 1.08	7.85 ± 0.20	1.65 ± 0.09	25.14 ± 1.42	Present work
215-30	66.64 ± 1.07	8.28 ± 0.20	1.60 ± 0.01	21.50 ± 1.44	Present work
250-2	64.77 ± 1.59	7.88 ± 0.09	1.59 ± 0.10	23.64 ± 1.64	Present work
250-16	67.73 ± 0.31	7.00 ± 0.07	1.57 ± 0.00	20.86 ± 0.66	Present work
250-30	66.31 ± 0.69	7.73 ± 0.15	1.68 ± 0.06	22.50 ± 0.57	Present work
250-30	67.8 ± 0.4	6.5 ± 0.0	1.4 ± 0.1	24.3 ± 0.4	[13]
220-90	61.1	6.4	0.9	NA	[54]
260-60	70.97±0.18	6.80±0.00	0.83±0.06	21.41±0.25	[17]
220-24	67.90	7.64	1.86	20.24	[15]
Lignite	49.70 - 73.91	4.25 – 6.23	0.80-2.82	12.97-24.40	[60]

342 **Note:** NA means Not Available

343 Table 3 exhibits the ultimate characteristics of raw material and hydrochars. Dry OP
344 contained 57.44% C, 7.39% H, 1.48% N, and 29.31% O contents. Hydrochar produced
345 under different severity conditions showed important variations in the C (58.03–67.73%),
346 H (7.00–8.28%), N (1.57–1.89%), and O (20.86–30.63%) contents. The S content was
347 found to be less than 0.02% in both OP and hydrochars and hence not reported in Table
348 3. The C content incremented by 2.25–17.85%, while the O content was reduced by 4.87–
349 28.85% in the hydrochars with the increase in process severity. In comparison to the
350 present results, earlier studies reported the same trend with slightly higher C (61.1–
351 70.97%) but similar H (6.40–7.64%), N (0.83–1.86%), and O contents (20.24–24.3%) in
352 OP hydrochars [13,15,17,54]. These differences are due to the use of varied HTC
353 conditions (220–260 °C, 30 min–24 h) and OP with different compositions in the
354 literature and present study. More severe process conditions enhanced the C content of
355 hydrochars because of intensified polymerization and aromatization reactions during
356 HTC. Whereas, the decline in O content was due to the dominance of dehydration,

357 decarboxylation, and deoxygenation reactions [52,61]. These reasons were also evident
 358 from the van Krevelen diagram of biomass and hydrochars (Figure 3). An increase in
 359 severity factors from 4.015 to 5.929 of the MHTC process produced hydrochars with
 360 relatively lower H/C (1.25–1.51) and O/C (0.24–0.32) atomic ratios than dry OP (H/C-
 361 1.53, O/C-0.40). This indicated an enhanced degree of carbonization in those hydrochars
 362 due to elevated dehydration and decarbonylation-decarboxylation reactions, respectively
 363 [62]. Hydrochars produced at greater severity factors (5.071–5.929) exhibited
 364 resemblance to lignite coal. Volpe and Fiori (2017) and Gultekin et al. (2022) also
 365 reported similar findings on hydrochars derived from OP [58,59].

366

367 **Figure 3.** van Krevelen diagram for raw material and hydrochars.

368 **3.3 Energy and moisture sorption characteristics of raw material and hydrochars.**

369 **Table 4.** Energy and moisture sorption characteristics of raw material and hydrochars
 370 on a dry basis

Samples	HHV (MJ/kg)	LHV (MJ/kg)	EDR	EY	EMC (mg/g)
OP	22.92 ± 0.24	21.44	1.00	100	123.3
180-2	24.46 ± 0.24	22.92	1.07	97.13	84.1
180-16	24.68 ± 0.22	23.10	1.08	98.25	84.7
180-30	24.67 ± 0.37	23.06	1.08	93.36	81.9
215-2	25.50 ± 1.09	23.88	1.11	79.06	70.4

215-16	26.09 ± 0.71	24.50	1.14	77.86	60.3
215-16	25.99 ± 0.38	24.40	1.13	76.64	61.5
215-16	26.07 ± 0.64	24.46	1.14	76.69	64.3
215-30	26.85 ± 0.39	25.13	1.17	64.10	61.6
250-2	27.24 ± 1.01	25.57	1.19	81.43	39.1
250-16	28.08 ± 0.54	26.44	1.22	77.58	36.4
250-30	28.75 ± 0.53	27.12	1.25	65.20	31.1

371

372 Table 4 presents the HHV, LHV, EDR, EY, and EMC of dry OP and hydrochars. The
373 LHV represents the more exact heating value of hydrochars after deducting the latent heat
374 of vaporization of water (calculated based on H content). EDR is indicative of energy
375 stored in a unit mass. The EMC is a crucial parameter for assessing the suitability of
376 hydrochars for fuel applications and plays a significant role in determining their long-
377 term storage stability and combustibility characteristics. It is derived from the moisture
378 sorption curve of biomass and hydrochars (Fig. S2). The rise in severity of MHTC led to
379 the production of hydrochars with beneficial fuel characteristics, i.e., higher HHV (24.46–
380 28.45 MJ/kg), LHV (22.92–27.12 MJ/kg), and EDR (1.07–1.25), along with reduced
381 EMC (31.1–84.7 mg/g). These properties were enhanced by 6.72–25.43, 6.90–26.49,
382 6.72–25.43, and 31.31–74.78% with comparison to OP, respectively. In accordance with
383 the present findings, previous studies also reported the same impact of process severity
384 on OP hydrochars characteristics. The OP hydrochar produced at the elevated MHTC
385 severity (5.929) showed a higher HHV (28.45 MJ/kg) than previously reported data.
386 Missaoui et al. (2017) reported that OP hydrochar, produced at 250 °C with a 30-minute
387 holding time, exhibited HHV of 27.6 MJ/kg and an EDR of 1.2 [13]. Similarly, Semaan
388 et al. (2022) observed an HHV of 25.6 MJ/kg and an EDR of 1.26 for OP hydrochar
389 produced at 280 °C with a 30-minute holding time [18].

390 The increase in heating value could be due to lignin enrichment in hydrochars with an
391 increase in process severity. Because lignin has a higher heating value than the cellulose
392 and hemicellulose fractions [39,63]. The increasing severity of MHTC caused a decline
393 in the cellulose and hemicellulose fractions due to their hydrolysis, but the lignin resisted
394 hydrolysis and got enriched due to its recalcitrant aromatic chemical structure. This is the
395 reason the hydrochar produced at high severity contained relatively higher levels of lignin
396 and HHV. This hydrochar also showed the relatively lowest EMC (31.1 mg/g), which
397 was reduced by 74.78% with respect to raw dry OP (123.3 mg/g). Data on the EMC of
398 OP hydrochars are not available in the literature for comparison. However, in agreement
399 with the present findings, Aguado et al. (2020) also reported that the most severe
400 conditions ($\log R_0 = 7.68$) reduced EMC in hydrochars derived from almond tree pruning
401 by 80% compared to raw almond tree pruning [37]. The decrease in EMC of hydrochars
402 with increased process severity could be due to the loss of hygroscopic hydroxyl groups
403 (characteristic of polysaccharides) and the enrichment of hydrophobic lignin fractions.
404 This increases the hydrophobic character of the material [64]. Lower EMC in hydrochars
405 is an indicator of their potential for better combustion performance [28,65].

406 **3.4 Slagging and fouling indices for raw material and hydrochars**

407 The mineral composition (Na_2O , K_2O , MgO , CaO , P_2O_5 , Fe_2O_3 , Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 , and TiO_2)
408 of dry OP and hydrochars are presented in Table S3 (Supplementary Information). On
409 basis of this data, different slagging and fouling indices (AI, B/A ratio, SI, FI, SVI, and
410 BAI) of dry OP and hydrochars were determined (Figure 4). The dry OP biomass
411 exhibited 1.17 kg/GJ AI, 20.59 B/A, 0.21 SI, 55.43 FI, 12.07 SVI, and 0.04 BAI.
412 Comparatively, hydrochars showed 0.16-0.92 kg/GJ AI, 4.76-11.12 B/A, 0.05-0.11 SI,
413 2.18-18.54 FI, 13.25-21.36 SVI, and 0.01-0.11 BAI. Hydrochar produced at the highest
414 severity showed relatively lower AI (0.16 kg/GJ), SI (0.05), and FI (2.18), which were

415 reductions of 86.53%, 76.89%, and 96.07%, compared to OP. The decrease in AI was due
416 to an increase in HHV and a decrease in K and Na content in high-severity hydrochar.
417 Lower SI was because of a reduction in basic oxides, retention of acidic oxides, and very
418 low S content in hydrochar. The decrease in the FI of hydrochars was due to the reduced
419 concentrations of alkali and alkaline earth metals. The SVI (21.03) and BAI (0.11)
420 increased by 75.11% and 165.22% in the highest severity hydrochar, respectively,
421 compared to OP. The SVI was elevated because of the enrichment of SiO₂ and the
422 deduction in the Ca, Mg, and Fe concentrations in the hydrochar. An increase in BAI can
423 be due to lower Fe concentrations in the hydrochar. Similar findings on hydrochar
424 produced from agricultural wastes [66] and sewage sludge [67] were reported in the
425 literature.

426 A ternary plot (Fig. 4) was also used to estimate the slagging-fouling risk based on the
427 initial deformation temperature (IDT) of minerals present in OP and hydrochars. Despite
428 the above-mentioned positive results about hydrochar in terms of slagging and fouling
429 indices, the ternary plot revealed the OP and its hydrochars are at high slagging and
430 fouling risk. The reason is that they contained a relatively higher amount of minerals with
431 low initial deformation (melting) temperatures, i.e., Na₂O, K₂O, and P₂O₅, than minerals
432 with higher initial deformation melting temperatures, i.e., CaO, MgO, Fe₂O₃, and Al₂O₃
433 [33]. This is problematic because silica could react with alkali minerals with low melting
434 temperatures and make eutectics that could cause slagging [34]. Nevertheless, a
435 progression of high severity hydrochars from the high slagging-fouling risk region to the
436 nearby medium region was observed.

437

438 **Figure 4.** Ternary plot with slagging and fouling indices for raw material and hydrochars.

439 **3.5 Response surface optimisation for hydrochar production with best fuel**
 440 **characteristics**

441 The experimental data regarding HY, EMC, HHV, and LHV were mathematically
 442 modeled by applying ANOVA analysis with a 95% confidence level. Table 5 shows the
 443 parameter values of the four mathematical models (Eq. 1), as well as the regression
 444 coefficients R^2 and R^2 adjust. In all cases, the models were statistically significant (p-
 445 values < 0.0001), while the regression coefficient (R^2), which represents the goodness-
 446 of-fit between experimental and predicted data, was higher than 0.991. This can also be
 447 seen in Fig. S3 for the four responses studied.

448 **Table 5.** Model parameters (β_i) and regression coefficients (R^2 and R^2 adjust) for the
 449 models representing HY, EMC, HHV, and LHV of the hydrochars.

450

Response	β_0	β_1	β_2	β_3	β_4	β_5	R^2	R^2 adjust
----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-------	--------------

HY, %	537	- 4.04	1.52	0.00869	0.0192	0.00626	0.991	0.983
EMC, mg/g	15.5	1.18	- 0.732	- 0.00433	0.0158	NS	0.994	0.990
HHV, MJ/kg	25.3	- 0.0361	- 0.106	0.000173	NS	0.000664	0.994	0.990
LHV, MJ/kg	24.7	- 0.0436	- 0.120	0.000186	NS	0.000719	0.996	0.993

451

452 Note: Models obtained from Eq. (1); Data are shown with three significant figures.; NS: not statistical
453 significance.

454

455 Fig. 5 shows the 3D response surfaces and 2D contour plots generated by applying Eq.
456 (1) with the parameters contained in Table 5 and for temperatures and reaction times in
457 the ranges 180–250 °C and 2–30 min, respectively. In the case of hydrochar yield (Fig.
458 5a), the highest values were obtained for the lowest reaction temperature (180 °C)
459 combined with low reaction times. Thus, the model predicted a maximum HY value of
460 92.8% under the conditions of 180 °C-10.6 min, in which mainly a loss of aqueous
461 extractives would occur. As can be seen in the coefficients plot, expressed in coded form
462 in Fig. S4-a, the value of HY is negatively influenced by two linear terms (T_R and t_R), a
463 quadratic term ($t_R \times t_R$) and an interaction term ($T_R \times t_R$), while the quadratic term ($T_R \times$
464 T_R) has a positive effect on HY. This leads to a reduction of the HY with increasing
465 temperature and time during the MHTC, although for higher temperatures the hydrolytic
466 effect is less pronounced, particularly for shorter reaction times. The mathematical model
467 also revealed that hydrochar recovery is strongly reduced above 220 °C for reaction times
468 exceeding 15 min, which could be explained by the fact that at this temperature cellulose
469 starts to undergo significant hydrolysis during hydrothermal treatments [63]. The
470 minimum value of HY (50.4 %) was achieved for the conditions of 243 °C-30 min.
471 Comparatively, Eres Yay et al. (2021) reported a slightly higher HY of 53% at a higher
472 temperature (260 °C) and longer holding time (60 min) than the present study [16]. This

473 suggested that MHTC could be used to achieve similar HY at a lower temperature and
474 shorter holding time, compared to HTC.

475 For the EMC of the hydrochars, the mathematical model showed that this parameter is
476 strongly influenced by the reaction temperature and, to a much lesser extent, by the
477 treatment time (Fig. S4-b). The mathematical model predicted a maximum EMC value of
478 86.5 mg/g for the hydrochar obtained at 180 °C-2 min and a minimum value of 31.9 mg/g
479 under the conditions of 250 °C-23.3 min (Fig. 5b). Considering that the EMC value for
480 the dry raw OP is 123.3 mg/g, the application of MHTC caused a significant reduction of
481 more than 74.0% in the EMC content of hydrochars. The experimental values of HHV
482 LHV showed excellent fits to the model (Eq. 1), as indicated by the R^2 data in Table 6.
483 According to Figs. S4-c and S4-d, temperature and reaction time exert a positive effect
484 on HHV and LHV, with the two linear terms of the models (T_R and t_R) being much more
485 significant than the quadratic term ($T_R \times T_R$) and the interaction term ($T_R \times t_R$). This
486 implies that the maximum values of HHV and LHV (28.9 MJ/kg and 27.2 MJ/kg,
487 respectively) are achieved by MHTC of OP at 250 °C for 30 min, as shown in Figs. 5c
488 and 5d. The HHV value for this hydrochar is similar to that reported by other authors (29
489 MJ/kg) when OP was hydrothermally treated at 240 °C for 60 min [16]. This study
490 represented an increase of the HHV by 26.1% compared to the original feedstock. In
491 another study, Cheng et al. (2022) reported an optimised condition at 220 °C-60 min for
492 coconut shell hydrochar production with a maximum HHV value of 29.39 MJ/kg [68].

493

494 **Figure 5.** Response surface plots corresponding to: (a) HY; (b) EMC; (c) HHV; and (d)
 495 LHV.

496 **3.6 Combustion performance of biomass and hydrochars**

497 The thermogravimetric (TG) curves (Figs. 6a and 6b) illustrate that heating both OP and
 498 hydrochar (250-30) led to a continuous loss of weight until reaching temperatures above
 499 600 °C, where the values stabilized and indicated the weight of the ash in the samples.
 500 Furthermore, the curves of the TG (Fig. 6b) and DSC (Fig. 6d) were divided into three
 501 zones (Zone 1, Zone 2, and Zone 3) to facilitate their interpretation. In Zone 1, from room
 502 temperature to slightly above 100 °C, materials undergo drying. Within this region, the
 503 DTG analysis of the raw OP exhibited a more pronounced signal of moisture, reinforcing

504 the notion that the hydrochar has a more hydrophobic character than the original biomass.
505 Zone 2 extends in the range of 141–375 °C for the raw OP and 120.8–403 °C for the
506 hydrochar. Here, thermal decomposition of certain biomass components (mainly
507 hemicellulose, cellulose, and, to a lesser extent, lignin) and release of VM occur. The VM
508 undergoes gas-phase combustion at temperatures above the ignition temperature (T_i),
509 causing the DSC curves to shift from negative values (due to the endothermic nature of
510 pyrolysis reactions) to positive values (attributable to the exothermic nature of
511 combustion reactions). For the raw OP, the DTG curve in Zone 2 displays a shoulder at
512 270 °C and a peak at 320.0 °C, which could be associated with the removal of VM
513 originating from hemicellulose and cellulose, respectively. Numerous studies have
514 reported that hemicellulose produces volatile compounds at relatively lower temperatures
515 compared to cellulose [69,70]. The DTG signal at 270 °C for the hydrochar 250-30
516 exhibited a significant reduction in VM signal compared to the raw OP. This could be
517 due to a loss of hemicellulose content in the hydrochar. On the other hand, the DTG peak
518 that appeared at 320.0 °C for the raw OP was replaced by a new signal of higher intensity
519 at 312.5 °C, in the hydrochar. This increase in signal intensity could be attributed to the
520 higher susceptibility of the treated cellulose to generate VM than the original cellulose,
521 considering the lower cellulose content of the hydrochar (3.0%) as opposed to the raw OP
522 (12.15%). The heterogeneous combustion of solids generated in Zone 2 takes place in
523 Zone 3. For the OP, a prominent peak at 420 °C and a shoulder centered around 460 °C
524 were observed (Fig. 7b). The first signal could be attributed to the combustion of
525 holocellulose fractions of the hydrochar, while the second signal could be from the
526 combustion of solids derived from lignin. The intense signal at 420 °C in the DTG analysis
527 of the raw OP was transformed into two small peaks at 419 °C and 428 °C in the hydrochar
528 250-30, which could be due to combustion of its cellulose and hemicellulose fractions.

529 Regarding the exothermic energy flows obtained from the DSC analyses (Figs. 6b and
530 6d), it was evident that MHTC caused a significant shift of signals from Zone 3 to Zone
531 2. Thus, for the dry raw OP, the energy emissions from combustion in zones 1 and 2
532 accounted for 31.3% and 68.7% of the total, respectively, with maximum heat flux values
533 of 106.3 kW/kg (Zone 2) and 224.4 kW/kg (Zone 3). In contrast, for hydrochar 250-30,
534 the emissions were 56.8% in Zone 2 and 43.2% in Zone 3, with maximum energy fluxes
535 of 140.2 kW/kg and 104.1 kW/kg, respectively. Therefore, MHTC resulted in a more
536 homogeneous biofuel in terms of energy, allowing for the generation of similar amounts
537 of thermal energy in both combustion zones. This could indicate that the combustion of
538 hydrochar, compared to the raw OP, is less intense and produces more stable flames.

539 From the thermogravimetric analyses, the values of $(dw/dt)_{max}$, $(dw/dt)_{mean}$, T_i y T_f were
540 calculated for both the raw OP (9.12 %/min, 1.04 %/min, 197.3 °C, and 498.4 °C,
541 respectively) and for hydrochar 250-30 (7.44 %/min, 1.06 %/min, 224.3 °C, and 533.4
542 °C, respectively). The higher T_i value for the hydrochar, compared to the raw material,
543 could be explained by its lower VM content and would imply a lower risk of spontaneous
544 combustion of the hydrochar. Cuevas et al. (2019) also obtained significant increases in
545 T_i when olive-fruit endocarps ($T_i = 251.4$ °C) were subjected to hydrothermal treatment
546 at 250 °C ($T_i = 294.5$ °C) [36]. The Comprehensive Combustibility Index (S) were $4.90 \times$
547 $10^{-7} \%^2 \text{ min}^{-2} \text{ °C}^{-3}$ (raw OP) and $2.94 \times 10^{-7} \%^2 \text{ min}^{-2} \text{ °C}^{-3}$ (hydrochar 250-30). The
548 literature suggests that values of $S > 2.0 \times 10^{-7} \%^2 \text{ min}^{-2} \text{ °C}^{-3}$ could be suitable for use as
549 biofuel [71]. Therefore, hydrochar 250-30 would exhibit good reactivity for use as a fuel,
550 although it would be lower than that exhibited by the raw OP.

551

552 **Figure 6.** TG curves (a, c) and DTG curves and exothermic heat flow curves from DSC
 553 analyses (b, d) under an oxidative atmosphere at $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ for the raw material and the
 554 hydrochar obtained at $250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30 min (250-30).

555 **4. Conclusions**

556 The present study demonstrated that microwave assisted hydrothermal carbonisation of
 557 olive pomace slurry from olive oil industry could be used to produce hydrochar fuel for
 558 potential combustion application. Temperature was found to be a major factor that
 559 directly governed the process severity, thermo-chemical reactions, and characteristics of
 560 hydrochars. The microwave-hydrothermal carbonisation at 180°C -30 min onwards
 561 resulted more noticeable depolymerisation of hemicellulose in the olive pomace.
 562 Whereas, treatment at 250°C (high severity) caused more aromatisation and lignin

563 enrichment in the hydrochars. Consequently, high severity hydrochars exhibited better
564 fuel characteristics (comparable to lignite), specifically in terms of lower ash content,
565 equilibrium moisture content, slagging-fouling indices, and higher fuel ratio, energy
566 densification, HHV, LHV, and combustion performance. The optimal microwave-
567 hydrothermal carbonisation process conditions were 250 °C and 30 min for the production
568 of olive pomace hydrochar, which is comparatively faster than an earlier reported
569 conventional hydrothermal carbonisation process (60 min and more). Moreover, the
570 microwave reactors used for hydrochar production could also be more sustainable, as they
571 don't pose any risk of reactor material corrosion and metal contamination, which
572 commonly occur in conventional mild steel reactors.

573 Major challenges for the practical application of high severity hydrochars for fuel
574 applications were identified to be their lower yield and bulk density, along with the
575 presence of minerals (containing potassium and sodium) with low melting temperatures.
576 Therefore, to resolve these challenges, future research studies on pelletisation of these
577 hydrochars using clay minerals (e.g., bentonite) are necessary. This will facilitate the
578 practical application of hydrochars as a substitute fuel for coal by making its
579 transportation and feeding easier and safer (less deteriorating) for cook stoves, industry
580 boilers, and power plants.

581 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

582 **Adnan Asad Karim:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding
583 acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Writing original draft,
584 and Review & Editing. **M^a Lourdes Martinez-Cartas:** Conceptualization, Data curation,
585 Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project
586 administration, Supervision, Writing original draft, and Review & Editing. **Manuel**

587 **Cuevas Aranda:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Supervision, Writing
588 original draft, and Review & Editing.

589 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

590 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
591 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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604 **Data Availability Statement**

605 Extended dataset with title “Production of hydrochar fuel by microwave-hydrothermal
606 carbonisation of olive pomace slurry from olive oil industry for combustion application”
607 for present publication are available on the Zenodo repository
608 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13695542>) This dataset can be openly accessed under
609 Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license, and includes following data
610 files: (1) Dataset description.txt (provides abbreviations or codes of samples and their

611 properties). (2) Extended dataset V1.0.xlsx (data files for the biochemical, proximate,
612 ultimate, HHV, and mineral characteristics of raw material (two-phase olive pomace
613 slurry) and hydrochars. (3) 13C-NMR data.zip (raw data files for 13C-solid nuclear
614 magnetic resonance analysis of raw material and hydrochars). (4) TGA-DTA data.zip
615 (raw data for thermal gravimetric analysis of raw material and hydrochars). (5) FTIR
616 data.zip (raw data for fourier transform infrared analysis of raw material and hydrochars).

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